

Building Climate Enemies:

Politics, Conspiracy, and
the Delegitimization of the
Environmental Agenda on
Telegram

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Key findings

- **Structural, not episodic, politicization:** Across all five periods analyzed (2018–2026), climate does not appear as a physical phenomenon but as an arena of political dispute. Extreme events such as floods, fires, and droughts are consistently mobilized to question the legitimacy of political adversaries, with Bolsonaro and Lula alternating in the role of negative protagonist.
- **Growing sophistication of information disorder:** The most relevant finding lies in the style of the messages, that is, in the genre and stance the text adopts. Until 2022, the delegitimizing content was expressed openly, in a combative-inflamed and promotional style. From 2023 onward, the same content begins to camouflage itself in a journalistic and analytical-neutral style. Disinformation does not retreat; it changes register, mimicking the credibility of sober news reporting.
- **Maximum discursive concentration in 2026:** The 2026 electoral period (P5) presents the highest concentration in the entire corpus: 62% of posts carry discourses of political instrumentalization of climate events, combined with a naturalizing genre and a journalistic style. The strongest triad in the corpus (instrumentalization × naturalizing × journalistic) appears multiple times during this period.
- **The Rio Grande do Sul floods as a pivotal event:** With 640 mentions, the Rio Grande do Sul floods are the most frequent climate event in the corpus, almost all of them concentrated in P4 (2023–2025). Their discursive treatment shifts from alarm to the accusation of incoherence and, in 2026, to naturalized instrumentalization as an incontestable political fact.

Content warning: *This technical note presents examples of posts extracted from conspiracy communities, including content that instrumentalizes climate tragedies for the purpose of political attack. The reproduction of these materials serves an analytical purpose and seeks to make visible the discursive patterns of climate information disorder in Brazil.*

Executive summary

Between 2018 and 2026, Brazilian conspiracy communities on Telegram produced a continuous corpus of information disorder about climate change, structured not by direct scientific denialism but by the permanent politicization of the environmental semantic field. The climate rarely appears in these spaces as a physical phenomenon; it appears as an arena of dispute between Lula and Bolsonaro, as proof of adversaries' hypocrisy, as an instrument of globalist control, or as a stage for electoral attrition.

The analysis of five periods (P1: 2018; P2: 2019–2021; P3: 2022; P4: 2023–2025; P5: 2026), based on the 20 highest-engagement posts per period that bore a relationship to the climate–politics theme, reveals an arc of increasing sophistication. Each period produces a distinct discursive pattern, determined by the interaction between the electoral or governmental cycle and the extreme climate events that cut across it.

The central finding is not one of content but of register: until 2022, the *delegitimizing* tenor circulated openly in a *combative-inflamed* and *promotional* style. From 2023 onward, the same content begins to camouflage itself in a *journalistic* and *analytical-neutral* style. In 2026, this camouflage is completely naturalized: the accusation that the political adversary exploits climate tragedies is presented as an incontestable press fact. Disinformation did not retreat; it merely changed costume.

This process is described in this note as semantic colonization: not the denial of scientific-environmental vocabulary, but its capture and the reversal of its valence. Terms such as climate change, Agenda 2030, and carbon are repositioned within adversarial discursive fields, where they come to connote foreign domination, elite hypocrisy, and loss of sovereignty. Fact-checking interventions that correct isolated factual claims have limited efficacy in the face of this process, because they operate on nodes of the chain without destabilizing the semantic architecture that produces them.

Extreme climate events function as discursive catalysts. The Rio Grande do Sul floods (640 mentions, almost all in P4; from 2023 to 2025) are the most illustrative case: the same event that could mobilize collective solidarity is converted into an arena of crossed accusations. When the flood occurs, the adversarial semantic field is already occupied.

1. Introduction

This technical note examines how information disorder about climate change operates within Brazilian conspiracy communities on Telegram, using Critical Discourse Analysis (Fairclough, 2001) as its analytical lens. The focus is not on identifying isolated false claims about the climate, but on the discursive patterns that structure their production and circulation: how certain discourses combine with particular genres and styles to produce specific meaning effects over time.

The theoretical perspective adopted is critical realist (Bhaskar, 1975; Sayer, 2000), which entails treating discourses not as mere representations of social and economic factors. Nor are they self-sufficient; rather, they are social practices that shape and are shaped by political, economic, and institutional structures. In practical terms, this means that the discourse–genre–style combinations identified in the *corpus* are not arbitrary; they respond to specific structural conditions, such as political polarization, electoral cycles, institutional distrust, and extreme climate events, and they produce regularities capable of shaping how the public perceives climate risk, evaluates institutional responses, and makes decisions.

2. Context and Literature

Climate information disorder in Brazil is not the spontaneous product of misinformed individuals. It is the result of a historically situated process in which the environmental agenda acquired an explicit partisan charge, with consequences that persist beyond the governments that produced them. During the Bolsonaro government (2019–2022), the federal Executive openly performed climate denialism, normalizing institutional distrust of environmental science as a legitimate political stance (Abessa et al., 2019; Ferrante & Fearnside, 2019). This normalization sedimented discursive structures that remain active even after the change of government, as the corpus analyzed here demonstrates.

The regime of truth about the climate. In Fairclough's (2001) perspective, discourses do not merely describe reality; they constitute subject positions, social relations, and systems of knowledge. The struggle over the

environmental semantic field (Bourdieu, 1996) is therefore not only a dispute over facts: it is a dispute over who has the authority to define what counts as legitimate knowledge about the climate, which actors are deemed trustworthy and which are suspect. The *corpus* shows how this struggle was waged systematically over eight years.

Interdiscursivity and its effects. Fairclough (2001) introduces the concept of interdiscursivity to describe how genres, discourses, and styles from distinct orders of discourse combine within a single discursive event. The central finding of this note (the progressive camouflage of delegitimizing content in a journalistic style) is precisely a phenomenon of interdiscursivity: the *Alarmist* genre and the *Conspiratorial* discourse of the political field adopt the style and format of the journalistic field, producing a hybridization that makes the disinformative content less recognizable and more shareable.

Information disorder in a disaster context. The literature on disinformation during extreme events (Starbird et al., 2014; Chou et al., 2018; Ricard et al., 2025) documents the pattern that the corpus confirms: climate events generate spikes in the circulation of false or misleading content about causes, those responsible, and solutions. What the corpus adds to this literature is the temporal dimension: it is not merely a matter of reactive spikes, but of a continuous discursive process in which each new event is integrated into a pre-existing narrative of politicization, confirming and reinforcing already-sedimented framings.

3. Methodology

The methodology of this study is organized into two subsections: **3.1. Data extraction and processing**, which describes the process and tools used to collect information from the Telegram communities and the criteria and methods applied to classify and anonymize the collected data; and **3.2. Data analysis** which details the quantitative and qualitative methods employed to investigate the connections, time series, content, and discourses in the Telegram conspiracy communities analyzed here.

3.1. Data collection and processing

This study uses the database of conspiracy communities on Telegram Brazil, collected through TelegramScrap (Silva, 2023), an open-source tool that uses the Telegram API via the Telethon library to extract content from open

groups and channels. All data were anonymized in compliance with the LGPD (Law No. 13.709/2018) to ensure privacy and adherence to ethical research standards. This anonymization process is not limited to user data but also includes the identification of the communities, ensuring that no group, channel, or participant can be traced through this study. Thus, although the data analyzed come from publicly available content, layers of privacy protection were implemented to prevent any form of direct attribution, reinforcing the ethical commitment to user confidentiality. The communities were identified through keywords, Telegram recommendations, and a snowball approach.

Two lexical searches were conducted (Box 1), both crossing climate terms with political references (Lula, Bolsonaro): Search 01 used general climate terms (climate, environment, climate change, greenhouse effect, Agenda 2030, among others); Search 02 used extreme-climate-event terms (fire, flooding, flood, drought, cyclone, heat, smoke, among others). A third search on disaster solidarity (BASE B) was identified but was not operationalized in this version.

Box 1 | Keywords used for data collection

BASE A			
Climate-related keywords			Politics-related
General phenomenon	'clima', 'meio ambiente', 'el niño', 'la niña', 'mudança climática', 'mudanças climáticas', 'efeito estufa', 'tipping point', 'agenda climática', 'agenda do clima', 'agendas do clima', 'agendas climáticas', 'agenda 2030', 'agenda ONU', 'agenda da ONU',	AND	'lula', 'bolsonaro'
Extreme climate event	'incêndi', 'inund', 'enchente', 'desliza', 'alaga', 'calor', 'aquecimento global', 'ciclone', 'tempestade', 'vendaval', 'geada', 'chuva', 'seca', 'desertificação', 'estiagem', 'transborda', 'enxurrada', 'maré', 'veranico', 'fumaça', 'qualidade do ar', 'desmorona'	AND	'lula', 'bolsonaro'

Source: prepared by the authors

After merging Searches 01 and 02 to form BASE A, we applied two exclusion criteria in the first filtering stage. The first was the **nationality of the group**: we retained only messages linked to Brazilian groups, in order to ensure that the analysis was anchored in Brazil's discursive, political, and cultural context. The second criterion was the **nature of the group**: we concentrated the analysis on groups previously categorized in our

database as conspiratorial, since we understand that this segment offers greater analytical density for identifying the discursive patterns we investigate, especially the articulations among climate denialism, institutional distrust, and the circulation of disinformation. This initial cut reduced the corpus from approximately 44 thousand to around 14 thousand messages.

In the pre-processing stage, URLs were partially normalized; residual domain fragments (such as "gglobocom", derived from "g1.globo.com") may appear in the frequent-term lists. Their presence is interpreted as an indicator of the volume of link-sharing to certain sources, not as an autonomous lexical term.

3.2. Data analysis

The analysis combined mixed methods. The quantitative stage mapped the presence and temporal evolution of climate events mentioned in the corpus, by period and by event type. The qualitative stage applied Critical Discourse Analysis (Fairclough, 2001) to the highest-engagement posts (sum of reactions). The 20 posts with the highest total number of reactions per period that bore a relationship to the climate–politics theme were selected for interpretive relevance, not statistical representativeness. During the analysis, messages unrelated to the themes of climate, environment, disasters, and related topics were excluded, as they did not constitute a relevant object for the purposes of this research, as were fully duplicated messages, in order to avoid the over-representation of identical content in the corpus.

Each post was classified simultaneously across three dimensions (Box 2): Discourse (ways of explaining reality), Genre (ways of acting socially), and Style (ways of being and affective positioning). The analysis sought to identify recurring combinations (discourse–genre–style triads) that constitute the dominant interdiscursive clusters in each period. Iterative readings by more than one researcher controlled for individual biases.

Box 2 | Analytical dimensions: Discourse, Genre, and Style

DISCOURSE
(ways of explaining reality)

Category	Description
Climate agenda as external imposition (D1)	Policies, agreements, and institutions responding to climate change (COP, the Paris Agreement, Agenda 2030) are represented as instruments of oppression, economic exploitation, or geopolitical domination, rather than as legitimate responses to environmental problems. The underlying logic is conspiratorial.
Accusation of incoherence in the climate agenda (D2)	Discourses that point to supposed contradictions between what climate actors, institutions, or movements claim to defend and their practices, priorities, or behaviors. The climate agenda is delegitimized through accusations of hypocrisy, moral selectivity, or double standards, such as criticisms of international travel, participation in elite forums, spending deemed excessive, or selective forms of solidarity in the face of tragedies.
Conspiratorial (D3)	The climate agenda is inserted into a broader worldview based on hidden coordination and control (New World Order, depopulation, biotechnological control, occultism/extraterrestrials, "the plan").
Response to extreme climate events (D4)	Concrete climate events (droughts, floods, storms, heatwaves) are mobilized as problems demanding practical, technological, or governmental solutions. Global climate change may or may not be acknowledged as the cause; the focus is on the response to the event, not on its systemic explanation.
Political instrumentalization of the climate agenda (D5)	Extreme events are used as an arena of partisan or moral dispute, with no relation to the response to the disaster itself. The event is mobilized for argumentative ends disconnected from the climate. Leaders are portrayed as absent or negligent.
Discrediting of climate actors (D6)	Environmentalists, NGOs, scientists, and international leaders are represented as hypocrites, manipulators, or instrumental; they defend the climate but have other interests (political, economic, geopolitical).
Climate as a positive agenda or opportunity (D7)	Climate and environmental issues (emissions, deforestation, recycling, renewable energy, mobility) are presented as opportunities for economic development, job creation, international cooperation, or modernization. The environment is neither a threat nor a battlefield — it is a resource to be valued. Typically associated with governmental communication that presents public policies as solutions reconciling growth and sustainability; also with the discourse of governments that adopt a progressive environmental agenda.
Climate change as catastrophes with devastating effects (D8)	Extreme events understood as causes of destruction and death, regardless of their causes.
GENRE <i>(ways of acting socially)</i>	
Category	Description

Legitimizing (G1)	Constructs a line of reasoning that justifies or grounds a political decision already taken or under way (withdrawing the offer to host a COP, leaving the Paris Agreement, obstructing Agenda 2030). The action comes first; the discourse comes afterward to clothe it in rationality.
Validating (G2)	Validates an interpretive framework or an intellectual authority, conferring legitimacy on them through deference, citation of works, or demonstration of alignment. It legitimizes not a specific decision but a system of thought.
Programmatic (G3)	Enumerates commitments, projects, or solutions attributed to a candidate or government, constructing an image of capacity for action and resolution. The action has not yet happened; it is prospective. It applies to any actor that announces a program of climate or environmental action.
Alarmist (G4)	The text signals an imminent or ongoing threat and summons attention, vigilance, or reaction. The tone is one of urgency, and the social action proposed is defensive.
Denunciatory (G5)	Denounces or reveals a supposed hidden truth about actors, institutions, or agendas, attributing to them illegitimate intentions, ulterior interests, or harmful actions. The projected identity is that of someone who "knows what is behind it" and has a moral duty to make public what others hide or omit.
Mobilizing (G6)	The text instructs or mobilizes the audience toward collective action or identity alignment (sharing, resisting, refusing, pressuring institutions).
Naturalizing (G7)	Records an "obvious truth" in a pseudo-neutral manner, erasing premises and framings; reality is presented as simply being what it is.
Storytelling (G8)	Narrates lived experiences, exemplary cases, or moral tales to generate identification and persuasion.

STYLE
(ways of being and affective positioning)

Category	Description
Scientific (evidence or experience) (E1)	Performs objectivity through external sources: cited studies, empirical data, personal experience, or the authority of recognized figures. The projected identity is that of someone who "researched", "read", or "discovered", regardless of the actual quality of the sources.
Promotional (E2)	The text adopts a promotional, enumerative, and optimistic register, projecting an image of effectiveness and resolution associated with a candidate or government. The projected identity is that of a supporter or promoter.
Analytical-neutral (E3)	The text demonstrates objectivity through scenario analysis, political-strategic reasoning, and its own argumentative construction. The projected identity is that of a rational observer, even when the conclusions are partial.
Combative-inflamed (E4)	The text is aggressive and polarized, using capital letters, insults, emojis, and categorization of the enemy. The projected identity is that of militant indignation.

Reverential (E5)	Expresses deference and admiration toward an intellectual or authority figure.
Messianic-inspirational (E6)	Liturgical structure, "New World Order" language, savior figures (Trump, Bolsonaro, galactic brothers), prophetic tone.
Journalistic (E7)	The text takes on the register of someone transmitting information in real time: it reports facts, cites sources and statements, and uses urgency markers (🔴, "URGENT", "NOW"). The projected identity is that of an informational intermediary; someone relaying what is happening, without explicit analytical or emotional elaboration.
Ironic (E8)	The text delegitimizes its target through derision and sarcasm, presenting it as laughable rather than refuting it. The projected identity is that of someone who exposes the adversary's ridiculousness and places themselves above it.

Source: prepared by the authors

The analysis spans five periods: P1 (2018: electoral campaign year); P2 (2019–2021: Bolsonaro government); P3 (2022: electoral campaign year); P4 (2023–2025: Lula government); P5 (2026: electoral campaign year). The periodization follows the political logic of the corpus, not merely the calendar: electoral cycles and governmental cycles produce distinct discursive patterns, which the analysis confirmed empirically.

A methodological observation about P1 (2018) is necessary. Unlike the other periods (N=20), the qualitative corpus for P1 comprises only five posts that simultaneously meet the criteria of thematic relevance and minimum engagement. This is due to two combined factors: Telegram was still a platform in its early adoption in Brazil in 2018, with a content volume incomparably smaller than that of subsequent periods; and the intersection of climate, politics, and high engagement was rare at that moment, prior to the consolidation of the conspiratorial ecosystem analyzed here. The conclusions about P1 should be read as the identification of an embryonic register (patterns that appear in isolated form and that the following periods will develop with greater volume, variety, and sophistication), not as a basis for statistical claims about the distribution of categories. In particular, the absence of interdiscursive clusters in P1 does not indicate the absence of a pattern, but rather an insufficient sample for its identification.

4. Results

4.1. Overview: Lula vs. Bolsonaro and Extreme Climate Events

Before examining the discursive patterns period by period, we present the time series of mentions of Lula vs. Bolsonaro during the periods studied (2018 to 2026).

Chart 1 presents the distribution of mentions of Lula and Bolsonaro across the five periods. In P1 (2018) and P2 (2019–2021), mentions of Bolsonaro are more frequent than those of Lula (632 against 151 in P2). From P3 (2022) onward, this distribution changes: mentions of Lula grow sharply and come to surpass those of Bolsonaro from 2023, still with a narrow gap in the P4 total (3,916 against 3,217). An increase in mentions of Bolsonaro is also observed in 2025. In P5 (2026), the two values fall and converge (375 and 343).

Chart 1 | Mentions of Lula vs. Bolsonaro by analysis period

Source: prepared by the authors

These movements broadly track the presence of each figure on the political scene in the respective period, as well as the total volume of content collected (substantially larger in P4). It is worth emphasizing that the frequency of mentions is a strictly quantitative proxy that does not capture the meaning, tone, or valence of the references (a mention may be supportive, critical, or neutral). The indicator serves, above all, to illustrate the degree of politicization of the debate over time — that is, the extent to

globalism, anticipating, in miniature, the repertoire that the following periods will develop with greater volume and sophistication.

"Paris and France are in flames because of the UN's Paris Agreement [...] Brazil is a signatory. BOLSONARO'S BRAZILIAN GOVERNMENT IS NOT GOING TO THROW THIS GARBAGE IN THE TRASH, WHICH ONLY SERVES TO ROB THE PEOPLE THROUGH THE HYPER-TAXATION OF THE ECOLOGICAL TAX BY THESE SOCIALIST, NAZI-FASCIST, COMMUNIST THIEVES UNDER THE NEW MADE-UP NAME OF GLOBALISM?" (P1)

Conspiracy community on "Globalism", November/2018

The list of most frequent terms in P1 confirms and specifies the founding register: "bolsonaro" (57) dominates in isolation, followed by terms from the legal-political semantic field ("crime", "lei", "projetos") and from national belonging ("brasil", "povo"). The almost total absence of climate vocabulary (no term related to the climate, the Amazon, or the environment appears in the top 20 positions) is itself a piece of data: in this period the climate enters exclusively as the backdrop of political dispute, never as an object of concern or debate in its own right.

4.2.2. P2 (2019–2021): Bolsonaro Government – governmental showcase and conspiratorial cosmology

The period is marked by two coexisting and complementary discursive projects. The first, dominant in volume, is the governmental showcase: posts that list government actions in response to climate disasters, combining a discourse of response to events with a *Legitimizing* genre (G1) and a *Promotional* style (E2). The rhetorical structure is characteristic: the text begins by attacking critics ('To the misinformed/ill-intentioned...!'), shields the message before presenting it, and ends with figures and the president's personal signature. This triad appears three times in the P2 corpus.

Figure 2 | Most frequently mentioned words in Period 2 content (2019–2021)

P2 (2019–2021) — 3,442 posts

1. bolsonaro: 901
2. brasil: 653
3. batalhão: 631
4. rua: 570
5. presidente: 476
6. centro: 470
7. infantaria: 435
8. povo: 408
9. stf: 402
10. militar: 398
11. vai: 350
12. guerra: 309
13. comando: 297
14. agora: 287
15. todos: 285
16. contra: 285
17. governo: 276
18. cachorro: 264
19. país: 261
20. corte: 254

Source: prepared by the authors

The second project, less frequent but analytically richer, is the conspiratorial cosmology. The UN's Agenda 2030 is presented as proof that Bolsonaro “knows what is to come”: confrontation with the New Order becomes an act of sovereign heroism. The messianic-inspirational style (E6) here fulfills a specific function: it summons not pragmatic action but identity adherence. Whoever “sees” the climate conspiracy is the awakened citizen; whoever does not see is the “cattle”.

"Brazil places itself practically alone against the New Order. Our president is a courageous visionary [...] What unites against us are the greatest and darkest powers on Earth. There is an unimaginable abundance in the Amazon that the world's vultures are preparing to usurp." (P2)

General conspiracy community, December/2021

The P2 word cloud (Figure 2) renders, in terms of frequency, what the discourse analysis identified qualitatively. "Bolsonaro" (901) and "Brasil" (653)

head the list, but what stands out is the dense presence of militarized vocabulary: "batalhão" (631), "rua" (570), "infantaria" (435), "centro" (470), "comando" (297), "militar" (398). These terms do not belong to the climate semantic field, but to the semantic field of grassroots political mobilization, of the call to resistance. They confirm that, even when the discourse is one of "response to extreme events", the underlying register is that of identity confrontation: the governmental showcase is built upon a substrate of summons to the culture war.

4.2.3. P3 (2022): Campaign Year – Irony as an electoral weapon

In P3, "Bolsonaro" (1206) and "Brasil" (841) retain the lead, but "Lula" (492) enters for the first time with significant weight, signaling the bilateralization of the discursive field that the electoral year imposes. The militarized vocabulary of P2 persists ("batalhão", "infantaria", "comando"), but "mundo" (447) and "grande" (351) point to the global scale of the denounced threats, consistent with the presence of figures such as DiCaprio, Macron, and Soros in the qualitative corpus. Derision as an electoral weapon finds its lexical counterpart: the adversary is small before the global scenario that conspiracism summons.

In the conspiracy communities, the discrediting of climate actors grows in presence and there is a change of method: alongside frontal confrontation (conspiratorial × denunciatory × combative), irony emerges as an instrument of delegitimization. The discrediting × denunciation × ironic triad appears twice, both around foreign figures (DiCaprio, Macron) whose eco-activism is ridiculed, not refuted.

"AGAIN, Leonardo DiCaprio lying about the Amazon. Comment on the President's thread, let's support him. Post materials and videos of recent fires in California and other countries." (P3 — mobilization through derision)

Conspiracy community on "Globalism", July/2022

Derision is discursively more efficient than refutation in certain contexts: it lowers the symbolic cost of rejecting a position without requiring counter-arguments. The post reporting Bolsonaro's 'sarcastic response' to DiCaprio need not demonstrate that DiCaprio is wrong — it is enough to

frame him as ridiculous. The P3 corpus reveals that irony is not merely a style: it is a genre of political action.

Figure 3 | Most frequently mentioned words in Period 3 content (2022)

Source: prepared by the authors

4.2.4. P4 (2023–2025): Lula Government – journalistic camouflage

The most striking turn in the entire corpus is visible in the P4 word cloud (Figure 4). "Lula" (5239) surpasses "Bolsonaro" (4117) for the first time — an inversion that documents the change of target described in the qualitative analysis. But the most revealing fact is the entry of "maligno" (2183) and "comunistas" (1878) among the most frequent terms, alongside "sistema" (4147) and "financeiro" (2174): the adversarial semantic field keeps its conspiratorial architecture intact, merely replacing the protagonist. "Fumaça" (1580) is the only term with a direct climate reference in the top 20 positions, and its presence confirms that the extreme events of P4 (wildfires, droughts) entered the corpus predominantly as political ammunition, not as an object of environmental analysis.

🌟 URGENT — BBC denounces that Lula is cutting down the Amazon Rainforest to build a four-lane highway for the climate summit!" (P4 — conspiracy in headline format)

General conspiracy community, March/2025

The rain that floods the COP30 venue in November 2025 is treated as discursive proof: 'Rain floods COP30 and shows the total lack of preparedness of the Lula government'. The concrete climate event, the rain in Belém, a city known for heavy rainfall, is reappropriated as an argument against climate policy, in a second-order gesture of semantic colonization.

4.2.5. P5 (2026): Campaign Year – naturalization as the point of arrival

The P5 word cloud reveals the most significant structural change of the entire arc: "notícias" (882), "click" (876), and "publicado" (874) lead, surpassing the names of the political leaders. For the first time, the dominant vocabulary is not that of political identity but that of the informational format. This inversion is the most direct lexical evidence of the journalistic camouflage phenomenon: the semantic field of news colonized the surface of the political-climate discourse. "Lula" (436) and "Bolsonaro" (351) remain, but they are subordinated to the register of information transmission. The presence of "gglobocom" (probably a fragment of G1/Globo URLs) confirms that traditional media outlets function simultaneously as a source of borrowed credibility and as a target of delegitimization in this period.

Figure 5 | Most frequently mentioned words in Period 5 content (2026)

P5 (2026): Lula Government – Naturalization as the point of arrival

efforts' — which is written as a complete news report (scene, character, editorial frame), but what it does is accuse the government of silencing criticism during a calamity. The accusation is not presented as an accusation: it is presented as a factual account. The text denounces the adversary for instrumentalizing tragedies while at the same time instrumentalizing that very tragedy.

4.2.6. Evolution across periods

Figure 6 presents a heat map of the frequencies of the analytical categories (discourse, genre, and style) distributed across the five periods of the corpus (P1: 2018; P2: 2019–2021; P3: 2022; P4: 2023–2025; P5: 2026), alternating between electoral campaign years and governmental cycles. The numbers indicate the quantity of items per cell; the intensity of the green color marks relative dominance within each period (P1 has N=5; the others, N=20).

The discourse axis

The most persistent category throughout the entire *corpus* is *Climate agenda as external imposition* (D1), present in every period, peaking in P1 (4 of 5 items) and returning markedly in P5 (3). This is the founding register identified in the qualitative analysis: the climate framed as a sovereign threat, never as a physical phenomenon.

Response to extreme climate events (D4) peaks in P2 (6), declining progressively, which is consistent with the role of the governmental showcase in the Bolsonaro period. *Climate as a positive agenda* (D7) is concentrated in P2 and P3 (5 and 3, respectively), reflecting pro-government communication during Bolsonaro's first term.

Conspiracism (D3) is the most stable narrative thread from P2 onward, with frequencies of 4, 7, 7, and 4, reaching its joint peak in P3 and P4, precisely the periods of greatest electoral dispute and change of government. *Discrediting of climate actors* (D6) is essentially a P3 phenomenon (4), the electoral year in which DiCaprio, Macron, and Greta Thunberg are mobilized as targets of derision.

Figure 6 | Distribution matrix of discourses, genres, and styles by period (P1–P5)

	P1 2018 campanha	P2 2019-21 governo	P3 2022 campanha	P4 2023-25 governo	P5 2026 campanha
DISCOURSE					
Agenda climática como imposição externa	4	3	2	1	3
Resposta a eventos climáticos extremos	1	6	4	3	.
Clima como agenda positiva ou oportunidade	.	5	3	3	.
Conspiracionista	.	4	7	7	4
Descrédito dos atores climáticos	.	1	4	1	1
Acusação de incoerência na agenda climática	.	.	.	4	3
Catástrofes de efeitos devastadores	.	.	.	1	.
Instrumentalização política de eventos climáticos	.	1	.	.	10
GENRE					
Legitimador	2	6	6	2	2
Validador	1	.	.	.	1
Endossador	1
Programático	1	1	.	2	.
Mobilizador	.	8	4	2	.
Alarmante	.	2	2	9	2
Denunciatório	.	1	5	1	4
Naturalizador	1	2	2	2	8
Storytelling	.	.	1	2	3
STYLE					
Análítico-neutro	2	1	1	3	4
Reverencial	1	.	1	.	.
Científico	.	1	.	.	2
Panfletário	1	7	5	1	.
Combativo-inflamado	1	8	6	5	6
Irônico	.	.	4	.	2
Jornalístico	.	1	2	10	6
Messiânico-inspiracional	.	2	1	1	1

menor → maior % no período categoria dominante do período números = nº de itens (n: P1=5, demais ≈20)

Source: prepared by the authors

The *Accusation of incoherence in the climate agenda* (D2) emerges in P4 (4) and persists in P5 (3), marking the transition to the Lula government as a target: the same conspiratorial repertoire is reoriented to denounce the hypocrisy of the new occupants of power. Finally, Political instrumentalization of climate events (D5) is the absolute dominant category of P5, with 10 of the 20 items, which characterizes an unparalleled concentration across the entire corpus and signals that, in the 2026 electoral year, the extreme climate event became the main device of political attack.

The genre axis

The *Legitimizing* genre (G1) dominates P1 and P2 (2 and 6), functioning as support for pro-Bolsonaro governmental communication. The *Mobilizing* genre (G6) reaches its peak in P2 (8), confirming the convocatory and militant character of this period.

The major inflection occurs in P4, where the *Alarmist* genre (G4) explodes to 9, the highest value of any genre in any period except P5. This marks the passage from a register of summons to action to a register of alarm and urgency, compatible with the journalistic camouflage identified in the qualitative analysis. The *Denunciatory* genre (G5) grows consistently from P2 (1) to P5 (4), tracking the escalation of the attack on adversaries.

The *Naturalizing* genre (G7) is dominant in P5 (8), in sharp contrast with the preceding periods — which confirms the central finding of the analysis: in 2026, the political accusation presents itself as an obvious fact, dispensing with justification. *Storytelling* (G8) appears with some relevance in P4 and P5 (2 and 3), suggesting the growing use of individualized narratives to anchor the political-climate discourse.

The style axis

The *Combative-inflamed* style (E4) is the most persistent and transversal in the corpus, present in every period with frequencies of 1, 8, 6, 5, and 6. Its peak in P2 (8) coincides with the peak of the mobilizing genre, reinforcing the militant character of the Bolsonaro period.

The most significant finding of the style axis lies in the trajectory of the *Journalistic* style: practically absent until P3 (only 1 and 2 occurrences), it jumps to 10 in P4 (by far the highest value in the entire heat map) and remains at 6 in P5. This curve is the most direct quantitative evidence of the phenomenon of discursive camouflage: the same delegitimizing content

that circulated in a promotional and combative style begins, from 2023 onward, to present itself in the form of the sober news report.

The *Promotional* style follows the inverse path: high in P2 (7) and P3 (5), it retreats to 1 in P4 and disappears in P5. The decline of the *Promotional* style and the rise of the *Journalistic* (E7) style occur at the same turn (P3–P4), and this simultaneity shows how the content does not vanish but changes costume.

The *Analytical-neutral* (E3) style maintains a moderate and relatively stable presence (2, 1, 1, 3, 4), with slight growth in P5, suggesting that the register of technical sobriety complements the *Journalistic* (E7) style as a strategy for neutralizing the political nature of the content. The *Ironic* style (E8) is concentrated in P3 (4), confirming that derision as a discursive weapon is specifically an electoral phenomenon of 2022.

Synthesis

Read together, the three axes describe a coherent arc: from an avowedly militant and combative information disorder (P2), through the electoral honing (refinement) of derision (P3), arriving at the sophistication of journalistic camouflage (P4) and at the maximum naturalization of political instrumentalization (P5). The corpus does not show a retreat of information disorder over time; it shows its progressive invisibilization.

5. Discussion

5.1. The arc of sophistication: from convocation to register

Reading the five periods together, three trajectories take clear shape. On the discourse axis, conspiracism is the constant thread from P2 onward, but the thematic focus migrates from the external to the internal: it begins by targeting the climate agenda as a foreign threat, moves in 2022 to the discrediting of specific climate actors, and in 2023–2026 turns inward, denouncing the government's contradictions and accusing the adversary of instrumentalizing the climate. The discourse becomes progressively metalinguistic; that is, it speaks about the political use of the climate more than about the climate itself.

On the genre axis, the slide goes from *Mobilizing* (G6) and *Legitimizing* (G1) (2019–2022, the register of the call to action) to *Alarmist* (G4) (2023–2025)

and, finally, *Naturalizing* (G7) (2026). In practical terms, the material moves from 'act now' to 'be alarmed' and arrives at 'this is simply the obvious'.

The most relevant finding lies on the style axis. Until 2022, the material openly assumes its combative nature, with *Combative-inflamed* (E4) and *Promotional* (E2) predominant and the *Messianic* in support. From 2023 onward, the same delegitimizing and conspiratorial content camouflages itself in a *Journalistic* and *Analytical-neutral* (E3) style, reinforced by *Naturalization* in 2026. Disinformation does not disappear; it changes costume.

5.2. Interdiscursivity: what the triads produce

The analysis of the discourse–genre–style combinations reveals that the three axes are not simply parallel descriptive categories: they interact to produce effects that none of the three would produce in isolation (Fairclough, 2001; Resende & Ramalho, 2006). The table below synthesizes what the main combinations identified in the corpus produce discursively:

Box 3 | Effects of the dominant interdiscursive combinations

Discourse	Genre	Style	What the combination produces
Climate agenda as external imposition (D1)	Legitimizing (G1)	Analytical-neutral (E3)	Constructs technical credibility for sovereign rejection: the argument appears informed and rational, not emotional.
Conspiratorial (D3)	Mobilizing (G6)	Messianic-inspirational (E6)	Produces collective urgency and group identity: whoever sees the 'truth' has an obligation to act. The conspiratorial cosmology gains the force of a summons.
Discrediting of actors (D6)	Denunciatory (G5)	Ironic (E8)	Delegitimizes through derision, not refutation. The adversary is ridiculous, not dangerous, which lowers the symbolic cost of rejecting them.
Accusation of incoherence in the climate agenda (D2)	Alarmist (G4)	Journalistic (E7)	It is the most insidious combination: the conspiratorial content becomes invisible when wrapped in the form of news. The alarmism looks like a reporter, not a militant.

Political instrumentalization of the climate agenda (D5)	Naturalizing (G7)	Journalistic (E7)	The peak of sophistication: the accusation that the adversary exploits tragedies is presented as obvious and as a press fact. It denounces the other for doing exactly what the text itself does.
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Source: prepared by the authors

The concept of interdiscursivity (Fairclough, 2001; Magalhães, Martins & Resende, 2017) is central here: what the *corpus* documents is not the simple coexistence of distinct discourses, but their productive hybridization. When the *Alarmist* (G4) genre and the conspiratorial discourse of the political field adopt the style and format of the journalistic field, a combination is produced whose persuasive effect is greater than the sum of its parts; and whose disinformative nature is precisely more difficult to identify. The most analytically relevant combination is the one dominant in P5 (instrumentalization × naturalizing × journalistic) because it produces what critical realist theory calls “naturalized common sense” (Fairclough, 2001; Sayer, 2000): the accusation becomes invisible as an accusation by presenting itself as a press fact.

5.3. Semantic field and discursive field: the dispute over the vocabulary of climate

The interdiscursivity perspective gains analytical depth when articulated with the notions of semantic field and discursive field (Lyons, 1977; Bourdieu, 1996). What the *corpus* documents over eight years is not merely a sequence of posts with particular discourses, genres, and styles: it is a structured process of dispute over control of the legitimate vocabulary about the climate.

The semantic field of climate change (Lyons, 1977), constituted by the terms that make up its core of meaning — climate change, carbon, emissions, Agenda 2030, *tipping point*, resilience, climate agenda — does not possess a stable and neutral valence. In the legitimate scientific-environmental field, these terms describe risk, urgency, and the need for collective action. In the conspiratorial discursive field documented in the *corpus*, the same terms are systematically repositioned: climate change becomes an ideological marker of globalist imposition; Agenda 2030 turns into the nodal point of a chain of equivalences (Laclau & Mouffe, 1985) articulating the UN, the WEF, Bill Gates and, depending on the period, Lula or Bolsonaro. The process,

which we will here call *semantic colonization*, is not the denial of scientific vocabulary: it is its capture and the reversal of its valence.

This operation distinguishes the climate information disorder documented here from classic climate denialism. Denialism denies facts; semantic colonization captures the vocabulary of facts and redirects it. A *post* that employs the terms climate change, carbon, and Amazon to denounce the handover of national sovereignty to the globalists is not refusing the words; it is contesting the semantic field in which they operate. **This is why fact-checking interventions that limit themselves to correcting isolated factual claims have limited efficacy: they operate on nodes of the chain without destabilizing the semantic architecture that produces them.**

The discursive-field perspective, in the Bourdieusian sense (Bourdieu, 1996), illuminates the mechanism by which this dispute occurs. Adopting the “journalistic” or “scientific” style without the symbolic capital that normally confers it, that is, without a link to institutions of legitimate knowledge production, is a heterodox strategy of positioning within the field (Bourdieu, 1996): the symbolic value of the journalistic or scientific field is captured in order to reposition it within an alternative discursive field. The peak of the journalistic style in P4 (10 of 20 items) is, in this reading, less a change of form than a change of field strategy: the same content that in P2 circulated openly as a militant pamphlet comes to circulate as news, precisely because the symbolic capital of journalism is more transferable and less traceable than that of the pamphlet.

This articulation between semantic field and discursive field also explains a regularity that the frequency heat map makes visible, but which would remain opaque without it: the synchrony between the decline of the *promotional* (E2) style and the rise of the *journalistic* (E7) style at the exact moment of the change of government (P3–P4). This is not a change of content, since the conspiratorial discourses maintain comparable frequency between P3 and P4. It is a reconfiguration of field strategy (Bourdieu, 1996; Fairclough, 2001): when the government that the conspiratorial ecosystem supported leaves power, the adversarial discursive field needs to redefine its position. The adoption of the *journalistic* (E7) style is the response: migrating from the field of explicit militancy to the field of apparently neutral information, capturing its credibility without assuming its epistemic obligations.

5.4. Critical realism: structure, practice, and event

The critical realist perspective makes it possible to situate the findings of the preceding sections at three distinct levels that mutually condition one another without being reducible to one another (Bhaskar, 1975; Sayer, 2000; Fairclough, Jessop & Sayer, 2002).

At the level of events, we observe individual posts, each with its discourse, genre, and style. At the level of practices, we identify the recurring triads, that is, patterns that are not the work of a single agent but of discursive practices shared by communities with a common history, infrastructure, and framings, and which include the operations of semantic colonization and strategic positioning within the discursive field described in the previous section. At the level of structures, what the *corpus* documents is the reproduction of a broader discursive order: Brazilian affective polarization (Fuks & Marques, 2022), which transforms any event, including climate disasters, into a resource for political-identity dispute.

The articulation among semantic field, interdiscursivity, and critical realism makes it possible to specify, at this third level, what exactly is being reproduced. What is reproduced is not merely a list of false claims about the climate. What is reproduced is a structure of distribution of symbolic capital among discursive fields (Bourdieu, 1996), within an order in which the scientific-environmental field and the journalistic field have their vocabulary and their formats available for capture by agents who do not possess the capital that would normally produce them. This structure, in the terms of Fairclough, Jessop, and Sayer (2002), is semi-autonomous: it is shaped by non-discursive conditions (political polarization, electoral cycles, extreme climate events), but it retains its own power to produce knowledge, identities, and social relations (Fairclough, 2001). It is this semi-autonomous power that explains why it precedes and survives any individual post, any political figure, and any specific climate event.

It is this structural character that explains the most disturbing finding of the *corpus*: the political instrumentalization of extreme climate events in P5 is not a novelty, but the point of arrival of a process of structural consolidation spanning eight years and two complete governmental cycles. Climate information disorder is therefore neither episodic nor reactive: it is formative. It does not follow climate events; it discursively precedes them, making available, for each new disaster, an already-sedimented framing that distributes responsibilities, identifies hypocrites, and instructs on how to

position oneself. When the flood occurs, the adversarial semantic field is already occupied.

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